

PRODUCTIVITY OF BT COTTON BASED CROPPING SYSTEM IN CENTRAL VIDARBHA ZONE OF MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract

The research experiment was conducted at Agriculture Research Station, Yavatmal Research Farm under Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola consecutively in Kharif–Rabi–Summer seasons of 2020-21 and 2021-22 to identify the suitability of the profitable cropping system to enhance resource utilization in Central Vidarbha region of Maharashtra. The pooled results of Kharif–Rabi–Summer 2020-21 and 2021-22 seasons revealed that, the cropping system with medium duration kharif cotton cultivar (PDKV JKAL-116)–summer groundnut crop recorded significantly the highest crop equivalent yield (4120 kg ha^{-1}) with highest GMR (Rs. 231394 ha^{-1}), NMR (Rs. 152134 ha^{-1}) and B:C ratio of 2.92. However, kharif cotton with early duration cultivar (Ajit-5)– rabi chickpea cropping system (C_3) recorded the highest system profitability of Rs. 449 kg/day/ha, which was closely followed by cropping system C_6 i.e. medium duration kharif cotton–summer groundnut system (Rs. 430 kg/day/ha) system profitability.

Keywords: Cropping System, Cotton, Economics, System profitability

Introduction

The cotton (*Gossypium* spp.) is an important cash crop, popularly known as ‘white gold’ which plays an important role in economy of Indian farmers. India ranks first in area, in the world whereas, stands third in production. Maharashtra has one third cotton growing area compared to India 41.92 lakh ha area with the production of 85 lakh bales (Anonymous, 2015). The Indian agriculture is now facing second generation problems like lowering of water table, nutrient imbalance, soil degradation, salinity, resurgence of pests and diseases, environmental pollution and decline in farm profit. The crop diversification i.e. change in cropping system with may be an efficient alternative for conserving natural resource base and proving opportunity to fulfil rising domestic demand by increasing income levels.

In Vidarbha region due to erratic behaviour of rainfall availability of water is not adequate to sustain the crop. As a result irrigated cropping system in this region is neglected. Therefore, attempt has been made considering cotton as base crop cropping systems with rabi wheat, linseed, chickpea and summer groundnut and summer green gram crops. The water shortage leads to non availability of sufficient irrigation water for the rabi and summer crops and nutrient resource management were considered while framing the experiment. Thus, it is felt necessary to design efficient cropping system so as to cater the needs and sustain under appropriate use of resources use of the system.

Materials and Methods

To assess the effects of different cotton based cropping systems the field experiment was conducted at research farm of Agriculture Research Station, Waghapur Road, Yavatmal during consecutive Kharif–Rabi–Summer seasons of 2020-21 and 2021-22. (latitude lies between $19^{\circ} 26''$ and $28^{\circ} 42''$ N and longitude of $77^{\circ} 18''$ and $79^{\circ} 18''$ E and 451 meter above mean sea level). The climate of Yavatmal is semi-arid and normal annual precipitation is 926.30 mm received in 62 rainy days. The total rainfall received during the season of 2020 and 2021 at Yavatmal centre was 1119.5 mm in 53 and 1266.3 mm in 63 rainy days, respectively. The soil is clayey in texture and moderately alkaline in reaction. The organic carbon, total nitrogen, available phosphorus and potassium were 0.68 %, 0.06 %, 21.8 kg ha^{-1} and 354.9 kg ha^{-1} respectively. Treatments comprised of C_1 : Sole Bt Cotton (Mid-late duration), C_2 : Bt-cotton (Early duration)–Wheat, C_3 : Bt-cotton (Early duration)– Chickpea, C_4 : Bt-cotton (Early duration)–Linseed, C_5 : Bt-cotton (Early duration)–summer Moong, C_6 : Bt-cotton (Mid late duration)–summer Groundnut and C_7 : Bt-cotton (Early duration) + Pigeonpea (6:2 Farmer Practice, Rainfed) which were laid out in Randomized Block Design in replications. The early duration cotton cultivar Ajit-5 and mid late duration cotton cultivar PDKV JKAL-116 was used for present investigation. Crop management factors like land preparation, fertilizer, weed control and other cultural practices were followed as recommended for local area.

All the plant protection measures were adopted to make the crop free from insects and diseases throughout the year. The data were recorded on ten randomly selected plants of each plot of each replication related to growth, phenological yield and after harvest soil studies.

Results and Discussions

The pooled data pertaining to seed cotton, lint yield, number of bolls, sequence crop yield and crop equivalent yield in different cropping system under resource conservation during kharif-rabi-summer seasons of 2020-21 and 2021-22 are presented in Table 1. The number of bolls per plant and days to 50% flowering was significantly influenced by under different cropping system. Mid late duration sole Kharif Bt cotton and medium duration kharif cotton–summer groundnut cropping system noticed the highest number of bolls per plant (23.5 bolls/plant and 23.1 bolls/plant, respectively) and comparatively more days to 50% flowering than rest of cropping systems under study. Similar kind of results was recorded for seed cotton yield of different cropping systems for kharif cotton. The crop equivalent yield was significantly influenced due to different cropping systems. Medium duration kharif cotton – summer groundnut cropping system recorded significantly the highest crop equivalent yield (4120 kg ha^{-1}) over rest of cropping systems. Which was followed by early duration kharif cotton–rabi chickpea cropping system (3287 kg ha^{-1}). These results are in confirmatory with those reported by Walia *et al.*, (2010) and Patel *et al.*, (2019).

The pooled data presented in Table 2 reflected that, cropping system C_6 i.e. medium duration kharif cotton–summer groundnut cropping system recorded significantly highest gross monetary returns, net monetary returns and B:C ratio (Rs. 231394, Rs. 152134 ha^{-1} and 2.92, respectively) over rest of cropping systems. This was closely followed by early duration kharif cotton–rabi chickpea cropping system (Rs.184692, Rs.116382 ha^{-1} and 2.70, respectively).

Whereas, early duration kharif cotton– rabi chickpea (C_3) crop sequence recorded the highest production efficiency of 1238 kg/ha/day followed by medium duration kharif cotton– summer groundnut system (1160 kg/ha/day) crop sequence. The highest system profitability was registered with early duration kharif cotton–rabi chickpea cropping system (Rs. 449/ha/day). Similar kinds of results were reported by Singh and Ahlawat (2012) and Desai *et al.* (2022).

Conclusion

In Central Vidarbha Zone on Maharashtra kharif cotton– summer groundnut and kharif cotton–rabi chickpea are the profitable and biologically efficient cropping systems. Whereas, considering the kharif cotton crop duration for optimum resource utilization mid-late duration kharif cotton–summer groundnut cropping system found superior for higher monetary returns highly productive efficiency. Whereas, the higher system profitability (rupees per day per unit area

occupation) is noticed in early duration *kharif* cotton cultivar–*rabi* chickpea cropping system.

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Table 1: Effect of treatments on number of bolls, days to 50% flowering, seed cotton, lint yield and crop equivalent yield of system (Pooled data *kharif-rabi-summer* 2020-21 and 2021-22)

Treatments	No. of Bolls / plant	DF 50%	Seed cotton yield (kg/ha)	Lint yield (kg/ha)	Sequence Crop Yield (kg/ha)		Crop Equivalent Yield (kg/ha)
					Rabi season	Summer season	
C1- Sole Bt Cotton (Mid-late duration)	23.5	64	1940	701	--	--	1940
C2- Bt-cotton (Early duration)- Wheat	20.8	61	1571	553	2981	--	2620
C3- Bt-cotton (Early duration)- Chickpea	21.9	61	1579	542	1911	--	3287
C4- Bt-cotton (Early duration)- Linseed	20.8	61	1587	560	999	--	2449
C5- Bt-cotton (Early duration)- summer Moong	21.8	62	1573	550	--	665	2430
C6- Bt-cotton (Mid late duration)- summer Groundnut	23.1	64	2005	630	--	2194	4120
C7- Bt-cotton (Early duration) + Pigeonpea (6:2 FP, Rainfed)	20.1	61	1786	601	--	--	1786
Mean	21.7	62	1720	591	842	408	2662
Sem±	0.49	0.63	47	24.25	--	--	47
CD at 5%	1.52	1.94	146	74.73	--	--	145

Table 2: Effect of treatments on economics, relative productive efficiency, production efficiency and system profitability of system (Pooled data *kharif-rabi-summer* 2020-21 and 2021-22)

Treatments	Gross Monetary Return (Rs/ha)	Net Monetary Returns (Rs/ha)	Cost of production (Rs/ha)	B:C ratio	Relative Productive Efficiency	Cropping period (days)	Product ion Efficiency (kg/ha/day)	System Profitability (Rs/day/ha)
C1- Sole Bt Cotton (Mid-late duration)	108993	63184	45809	2.38	--	247.50	784	256
C2- Bt-cotton (Early duration)- Wheat	147192	80609	66583	2.21	35.05	255.50	1026	316
C3- Bt-cotton (Early duration)- Chickpea	184692	116386	68306	2.70	69.43	265.50	1238	449
C4- Bt-cotton (Early duration)- Linseed	137607	76631	60975	2.26	26.24	264.00	928	291
C5- Bt-cotton (Early duration)- summer Moong	136491	81533	54957	2.48	25.25	226.00	1075	361
C6- Bt-cotton (Mid late duration)- summer Groundnut	231394	152134	79260	2.92	112.37	355.50	1160	430
C7- Bt-cotton (Early duration) + Pigeonpea (6:2 FP, Rainfed)	100358	50075	50283	2.00	-7.92	195.50	914	257
Mean	149532	88650	60882	2.42	37.20	258.50	1018	337
Sem±	2639	2639	0.00	--	--	--	--	--
CD at 5%	8130	8130	0.00	--	--	--	--	--